

trifluoroacetylacetonates most probably have the penta-coordinated configuration.

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Studies on Mixed-Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) : Part VI—Copper Mixed-Ligand Complexes Containing Homo Donor Atoms

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MANY copper(II) mixed-ligand complexes containing oxygen and nitrogen as donor atoms were reported in our earlier papers¹⁻⁵. It was found that all such mixed-ligand complexes with hetero donors show marked preference for the formation of

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‡ Abbreviations : en=ethylenediamine, gly=glycinate,
lact=lactate, mal=malonate, ox=oxalate and
pn=1, 3-propylenediamine.

NOTES

mixed-ligand complexes over binary complexes. It was considered worthwhile to study mixed-ligand complexes of copper(II) containing only oxygen or only nitrogen as donor atoms to get a better idea of the magnitude of such preferences.

This paper deals with the formation constants of the mixed-ligand complexes formed by copper(II) with (i) ethylenediamine and 1,3-propylenediamine and (ii) lactate and oxalate/malonate. The studies were made by spectrophotometry and polarography, results from which may be compared with each other as a check on each other.

The details of the experimental techniques and the method of calculation are the same as given in our earlier^{2, 4} papers.

Results and Discussion

I. Copper-ethylenediamine-1,3-propylenediamine system :

A. *Spectrophotometry* : The method of Newman and Hume⁶ was applied to the determination of the formation constant of $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{pn})]^{2+}$ by spectrophotometry. The value of $\log \beta_{\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{pn})}$ obtained is 18.74.

B. *Polarography* : Reversible and diffusion controlled polarographic reductions occurred at moderate concentrations of the two diamines. The $E_{1/4} - E_{3/4}$ values are in the range of 0.030-0.035 V, corresponding to single step reduction involving two electrons.

Effect of pH : Polarograms were recorded each time after the change of pH of the solution containing Cu^{2+} and equal excess of ethylenediamine and 1,3-propylenediamine. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH is linear in the pH range of 9.3-9.7. The slope of the straight line is 0.053 corresponding to the involvement of two protons at the electrode reaction. The groups which get protonated are the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups, one each of the two diamines, the pK values for which are 9.89 and 10.62 in the case of ethylenediamine and 1,3-propylenediamine respectively. The electrode reaction may be represented thus :

The value of overall formation constant of the mixed-ligand complex, $\beta_{\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{pn})}$, calculated by the method of Schaap and McMasters⁷, for solutions containing varying concentrations of the two diamines and at different pH values in the range of 9-10, from the shift in $E_{1/2}$ values due to complexation are very nearly constant. The average value of $\log \beta$ is 18.83, comparing very favourably with the value 18.74, from spectrophotometry.

II. Copper-lactate-dicarboxylate systems :

A. *Spectrophotometry*: In the case of [Cu(lact)(ox)] and [Cu(lact)(mal)], as the *pK* values of ligands do not differ very much, there is no significant difference in the nature of absorption curves with changes in *pH*. With the [Cu(lact)(ox)] system, the concentration of oxalate and *pH* are to be selected carefully to avoid the precipitation of the highly insoluble [Cu(ox)]. This restricted the study of this system to a very narrow *pH* range. The formation constants of [Cu(lact)(ox)] and [Cu(lact)(mal)] were calculated by the method of Newman and Hume⁶. The values of log β calculated are 6.75 and 6.04 for [Cu(lact)(ox)] and [Cu(lact)(mal)] respectively.

B. *Polarography*: The two mixed-ligand complexes were studied polarographically by keeping the concentration of the weaker ligand, lactate, constant while varying the concentration of the dicarboxylate. It was not possible to vary the concentrations of the two ligands by mere change of *pH*.

In each of these mixed-ligand systems, a shift in half-wave potential to more negative values was observed with increase in oxalate or malonate concentration. The magnitude of this shift is greater in the presence of lactate than that obtained for the simple copper-oxalate or copper-malonate system. This is significant, as it indicates that in mixed-ligand complex formation lactate is the primary ligand and that the oxalate or malonate is the secondary ligand.

Fig. 1. Copper-lactate-malonate system. Effect of varying the malonate concentration on $E_{1/2}$ at *pH* = 4.60 and [lact] = 0.11M.

Effect of varying the secondary ligand concentration on $E_{1/2}$:

In order to arrive at the stoichiometry of these mixed ligand complexes formed, a series of polarograms were recorded with a constant concentration of Cu^{2+} and lactate ion (0.11 M) with varying concentrations of the dicarboxylate. The *pH* was maintained constant at 4.60. A plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log[\text{dicarboxylate}]$ is linear with a slope of about 0.031, indicating clearly the coordination of only one dicarboxylate to the 1:1 copper-lactate complex¹. Such a plot for the [Cu(lact)(mal)] as a representative system is given in Fig. I.

The formation constants of these mixed-ligand complexes calculated in the *pH* range 4.2-4.9 are very nearly constant. The values are listed in Table I along with the mixed-ligand stabilisation constant log X¹.

TABLE I—THE LOGARITHM OF THE OVERALL FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES AND THE VALUES OF LOG X.

S. No.	Complex	Spectrophotometry		Polarography	
		log β	log X	log β	log X
1.	[Cu(en)(pn)]	18.74 ± 0.13	0.99	18.83 ± 0.07	1.17
2.	[Cu(lact)(ox)]	6.75 ± 0.10	0.31	6.81 ± 0.04	0.43
3.	[Cu(lact)(mal)]	6.04 ± 0.06	0.45	6.09 ± 0.09	0.55

The log X values for [Cu(en)(pn)] is higher than the 0.6 predicted on statistical basis only⁸, indicating the favoured formation of this over the binary complexes. The log X value for [Cu(lact)(ox)] and [Cu(lact)(mal)], however, are not greater than 0.6. This does not mean that these complexes will not be formed at all. It simply indicates that such formation is not favoured over the binary complexes.

The log X value for [Cu(lact)(mal)] is higher than that for the [Cu(lact)(ox)], indicating that Cu^{2+} mixed-ligand complexes having a five- and a six-membered ring in the same complex is preferred over those containing two five-membered rings.

From our detailed study on mixed-ligand complexes of Cu^{2+} with nitrogen and oxygen donors it was observed that complexes containing both nitrogen and oxygen as donor atoms are preferred over those containing only nitrogen or oxygen as donor atoms. The log X values for some mixed-ligand complexes of Cu^{2+} with homo and hetero donor atoms calculated from polarographic data are listed below :

- [Cu(lact)(ox)]⁻ - 0.43 ; [Cu(ox)(gly)]⁻ - 1.48 ;
- [Cu(lact)(en)]⁺ - 2.62 ; [Cu(en)(gly)]⁺ - 1.71 ;
- [Cu(en)(pn)]²⁺ - 1.17.

These values show that Cu^{2+} has a general preference for coordination with nitrogen in preference to oxygen and this is in keeping with its classification as "intermediate" acid in the hard-soft system. The preference for mixed-donors over either all nitrogen or all oxygen donors is obvious. In the case of $[\text{Cu}(\text{lact})(\text{ox})]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{gly})]$, both have uninegative charge. Hence the only reason for the enhanced value of $\log X$ for $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{gly})]$ is due to hetero donors. Another example is the pair $[\text{Cu}(\text{lact})(\text{en})]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{gly})]$ each with unipositive charge.

The 1:1 copper-oxalate complex is highly insoluble and is precipitated under pH-titration conditions. In the present studies involving the use of spectrophotometry and polarography it has been found possible to avoid the precipitation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})]$ and these techniques have been found to be advantageous in the study of Cu^{2+} systems containing oxalate as a ligand.

In the case of lactate complexes, the studies indicate the coordination of the hydroxyl group in its unionised form, though such coordination is weaker than in its deprotonated form. Such participation may be important in biological processes such as metal-enzyme action, as it allows a rapid rearrangement of the complexes necessary for the enzyme to act as a catalyst.

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α -Iodoacetoacetanilide and Its Metal Chelates

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EARLIER studies using α -bromo and α -chloroacetoacetanilides^{1,2} have revealed that, contrary to expectation, these ligands have enhanced chelating ability than acetoacetanilide. In this connection it was of interest to examine the chelating tendency of α -iodoacetoacetanilide. However, only a very few of its com-

plexes could be obtained analytically pure, since the complexes are mostly insoluble in all common solvents.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by adding to a hot solution of acetoacetanilide (17.7 g, 0.1 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), iodine (10 g, 0.04 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) followed by iodic acid (3.44 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in hot water (5 ml). The mixture was refluxed over a water-bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled in a freezing mixture and the yellow precipitate formed³ filtered quickly, and washed successively with water, ice-cold aqueous ethanol, and petroleum ether, till the washings were colourless. The product was recrystallised from ethanol, when 17.6 g (58% yield, m.p. 126°) of the pure material were obtained. Found C, 39.51; H, 3.23; N, 4.51%. Calculated percentages, C, 39.62; H, 3.30; N, 4.62%. Infrared spectrum (Nujol mull) showed strong carbonyl bands at 1730 and 1660 cm^{-1} , and a medium intensity broad N-H stretching band at 3240 cm^{-1} . N.M.R. spectrum in CDCl_3 showed that the product is indeed α -iodoacetoacetanilide. Four absorptions, as expected, were observed at 0.78 τ (broad singlet for NH), 2.5 τ (multiplet for C_6H_5), 4.8 τ (singlet for α -CH) and 7.4 τ (singlet for CH_3). Integrated intensities agreed with the number of different kinds of hydrogen present.

Metal chelates of the ligand were prepared as follows :

Beryllium(II) chelate : To a stirred hot solution of ligand (0.02 mol) in ethanol (200 ml), a hot solution of beryllium sulphate pentahydrate (0.01 mol) in water (10 ml) was added dropwise. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 6-6.5 with dilute ammonia, continued stirring for 1 hr, and the precipitated complex filtered.

Copper(II) chelate : A solution of ligand (0.02 mol) in methanol (100 ml) was added to a stirred methanolic solution (50 ml) of copper(II) acetate hydrate (0.01 mol). After continued stirring for 2 hr, the crystalline precipitate formed was filtered.

Chromium(III) chelate : Chromium(III) chloride hexahydrate (0.005 mol) was dissolved in water (50 ml) containing urea (10 g). The ligand (0.03 mol, excess) in ethanol (50 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed for 9 hr. The precipitated complex was filtered hot.

Iron(III) chelate : An aqueous solution (50 ml) of iron(III) chloride (0.01 mol) containing sodium acetate trihydrate (3 g) was added to an ethanolic solution (100 ml) of ligand (0.03 mol), and the mixture stirred for 1 hr. The solution was then concentrated to 75 ml, and subsequently cooled in ice. The amorphous residue separated turned crystalline on trituration with petroleum ether.

Manganese, cobalt and nickel complexes : Aqueous solutions of manganese(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) salts yielded only insoluble and intractable crude materials with alcoholic solution of the ligand.